

Fuzzy logic direct torque control of induction motors using three-level NPC inverter

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ABSTRACT

Induction motor drives are extensively used for their robustness and efficiency, but precise control remains difficult under dynamic conditions. Conventional direct torque control offers a simple structure and fast response, but is limited by torque ripple, flux distortion, and poor low-speed performance. This paper proposes a fuzzy logic-based direct torque control (FDTC) combined with a three-level neutral point clamped (NPC) inverter. A fuzzy inference system (FIS) replaces the hysteresis comparators and switching table, while speed regulation is improved using a PI-fuzzy controller. MATLAB/Simulink simulations under speed variations and load disturbances demonstrate reduced torque and flux ripples, smoother flux trajectories, improved current waveforms, and faster transient response compared with classical DTC. These results confirm that the FDTC–NPC approach provides a robust and efficient solution for advanced applications such as industrial automation, renewable energy, and electric vehicles.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Induction motor (IM) drives are still used in current industrial systems because they are more robust, reliable, and cost-effective than DC machines [1], [2]. They are widely used in automation, renewable energy, and electric car applications where accurate torque and flux control are critical. Nevertheless, the nonlinear dynamics and parameter fluctuations of IMs make their control intrinsically difficult.

Following the advent of power electronics, multilevel inverter topologies, particularly the three-level neutral point clamped (NPC) inverter, have emerged as efficient solutions that provide decreased harmonic distortion, reduced voltage stress, and improved output quality [3]-[5]. Direct torque control (DTC), first developed by Takahashi and Noguchi [4] and later refined by Depenbrock [5], is well-known for its simple structure, quick torque response, and little reliance on machine parameters [6]. However, the standard two-level DTC has significant torque and flux ripples, as well as variable switching frequency, particularly at low speeds [7]. Advanced approaches, such as space vector modulation (SVM) [8] and model predictive control (MPC) [9], address these difficulties while increasing complexity and processing burden.

To address these constraints, intelligent control approaches have been implemented into DTC systems. Fuzzy logic control (FLC) has showed exceptional capacity to handle nonlinearities and parameter fluctuations while maintaining robustness and quick dynamics. The use of fuzzy reasoning allows for continuous voltage-vector selection, smoother electromagnetic transitions, and near-constant switching frequency [10]-[16]. Furthermore, coupling FLC with the enlarged voltage-vector set of the three-level NPC inverter increases flux trajectory smoothness, reduces total harmonic distortion (THD), and improves steady-

state efficiency. Despite these benefits, few research has thoroughly examined fuzzy inference mechanisms in multilevel inverter-fed DTC schemes. In particular, the combined use of fuzzy decision layers and the richer voltage-vector structure of three-level NPC inverters has received insufficient attention for increasing torque ripple suppression and low-speed robustness under dynamic operating conditions.

This work presents an improved fuzzy direct torque control (FDTC) technique for induction motor drives based on a three-level NPC inverter. The fuzzy inference system substitutes traditional hysteresis comparators and lookup tables for voltage-vector selection, and a PI-Fuzzy speed regulator improves adaptability and transient response. The proposed FDTC-NPC technique is tested using MATLAB/Simulink simulations under various load and speed situations, which show reduced torque and flux ripples, enhanced steady-state precision, and superior dynamic behavior when compared to classical DTC.

2. METHODOLOGY OF DTC AND THREE-LEVEL INVERTERS

2.1. Principle of conventional direct torque control

DTC, initially introduced by Takahashi and Noguchi [4] and later refined by Depenbrock [5], is a well-established technique for high-performance IM drives. It directly controls electromagnetic torque and stator flux without requiring coordinate transformations or pulse width modulation, offering a simpler and faster alternative to FOC [8]. As illustrated in Figure 1, the classical DTC structure includes a flux and torque estimator, hysteresis comparators, a sector selector, and a voltage vector switching table. The estimated torque and flux are continuously compared with their reference values, and the resulting control signals determine the inverter’s switching states. While DTC provides fast responsiveness and resistance to parameter fluctuations, it suffers from significant torque ripple and variable switching behavior, resulting in poor performance at low rotational speeds. These restrictions encourage the employment of multiple inverters and adaptive control techniques to increase torque smoothness, flux management, and stable state performance.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the conventional DTC applied to a three-level inverter-fed IM

2.2. Mathematical modeling

The dynamic behavior of the IM in the stationary (α, β) reference frame can be expressed by the stator voltage equations derived from the classical DTC formulation and vector control theory [2], [5], [7]-[9]. These components are given by (1).

$$V_{s\alpha} = R_s I_{s\alpha} + \frac{d\Phi_{s\alpha}}{dt} \quad V_{s\beta} = R_s I_{s\beta} + \frac{d\Phi_{s\beta}}{dt} \quad (1)$$

The stator-flux components are obtained by integrating the voltage equations, which form the basis of flux estimation in DTC schemes [2], [5], [8]:

$$\Phi_{s\alpha} = \int_0^t (V_{s\alpha} - R_s I_{s\alpha}) dt \quad \Phi_{s\beta} = \int_0^t (V_{s\beta} - R_s I_{s\beta}) dt \quad (2)$$

The stator flux is mathematically defined by (3).

$$\Phi_s = \sqrt{\Phi_{s\alpha}^2 + \Phi_{s\beta}^2} \quad (3)$$

The stator flux angle is determined using (4).

$$\theta_s = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\Phi_{s\beta}}{\Phi_{s\alpha}}\right) \quad (4)$$

These quantities are crucial for real-time sector identification and torque/flux control in DTC and FDTTC algorithms [7], [8], [17]. The electromagnetic torque developed by the machine is given by (5).

$$\Gamma_e = p(\Phi_{s\alpha}I_{s\beta} - \Phi_{s\beta}I_{s\alpha}) \quad (5)$$

This approach, developed by Takahashi and Noguchi [4] and revised by Depenbrock [5], provides the mathematical foundation for DTC. The (1)-(4) define the electromagnetic interaction of stator voltage $V_{s\alpha}, V_{s\beta}$, current, and flux vectors. They are numerically implemented in the DTC estimator to estimate the instantaneous electromagnetic torque and stator flux, which are then continually compared to their reference values using hysteresis controllers. The above formulation has undergone extensive validation for both traditional and multilevel inverter-fed DTC systems [8], [9].

2.3. Switching logic and sector selection

In conventional DTC, electromagnetic torque and stator flux from (1)-(4) are compared to references via hysteresis comparators, maintaining values within tolerance bands through real-time switching state adjustments [9], [10]. Two independent controllers for flux and torque generate binary outputs for example flux signal C_f which, combined with stator flux position (α, β) , select the applied voltage vector. This enables rapid torque response without coordinate transformations or PWM modulators [11].

$$C_f = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } \Phi_s < \Phi_{sref} \text{ (Flux must increase)} \\ -1 & \text{if } \Phi_s > \Phi_{sref} \text{ (Flux must decrease)} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

As shown in Figure 2, this two-level decision process stabilizes the flux amplitude around its reference value Φ_s^* and prevents excessive oscillations. The torque comparator, on the other hand, evaluates the torque error $\Delta\Gamma_e = \Gamma_e^* - \Gamma_e$ and generates a discrete control signal $C_T \in \{-2, -1, 0, +1, +2\}$, corresponding to large positive, small positive, zero, small negative, and large negative torque variations. This five-level quantization enables finer torque control and smoother electromagnetic transitions than conventional two-level methods [12], [13].

The DTC algorithm assesses both flux and torque error rate, estimates the stator flux sector using (4), and selects a voltage vector from the triplet (C_f, C_T, N) [12], [13]. A two-level inverter uses six 60° sectors in the (α, β) plane, but a three-level NPC uses twelve 30° sectors for better voltage-vector resolution and smoother flux transitions [14]-[16]. This selecting mechanism guarantees quick torque response and reliability under various loads. However, the limited vectors in two-level inverters generate torque ripple and variable switching frequency, which supports the NPC topology's superior steady-state and dynamic performance.

In stator-flux regulation, a two-level hysteresis comparator is employed to ensure the flux magnitude remains within a specified tolerance band of $\mp\Delta\Phi_s$. As shown in Figure 3, the comparator produces the discrete control signal $C_f \in \{-1, 1\}$, which signifies if the calculated stator flux exceeds its reference beyond the permissible hysteresis boundaries [9], [10].

Figure 2. Five-level hysteresis comparator used for electromagnetic torque regulation

Figure 3. Two-level hysteresis comparator for stator-flux regulation

When the estimated flux exceeds the upper limit of the band, a negative control action is implemented to diminish the flux magnitude; conversely, when it drops below the lower limit, a positive control action is enacted to restore it. This hysteresis-based technique guarantees that the stator-flux amplitude remains constrained around its reference value while maintaining the rapid dynamic response and structural simplicity inherent in traditional DTC schemes.

2.4. Extension to the three-level NPC inverter

In this topology, as illustrated in Figure 4, the total DC-link voltage E is symmetrically divided across two series-connected capacitors, producing three distinct output voltage levels per phase: $(+E/2, 0, -E/2)$ [18], [19]. This arrangement reduces voltage stress on switching devices and improves the output waveform quality compared to conventional two-level inverters

The switching states of the devices determine the instantaneous phase voltage V_i applied to the motor stator winding. The corresponding binary switching functions for the upper and lower branches can be expressed as (7).

$$S_{i1}^b = S_{i1} \times S_{i2}, S_{i0}^b = S_{i3} \times S_{i4} \quad \text{with the } S_i \in \{+1, 0 - 1\}, \tag{7}$$

The corresponding phase-to-neutral voltage of phase $i \in \{a, b, c\}$ is expressed as (8).

$$V_{i0} = \frac{E}{2} S_i = \frac{E}{2} (S_{i1}^b - S_{i0}^b) \tag{8}$$

Where $S_{i1}^b = 1$ corresponds to $+E/2$, $S_{i0}^b = 1$ corresponds to $-E/2$ and both equal to 0 represents the zero state connected to the midpoint through the clamping diodes. The output phase voltages (V_a, V_b, V_c) relative to the neutral point O are expressed as (9).

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E}{v} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \times \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} S_{11}^b \\ S_{21}^b \\ S_{31}^b \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} S_{10}^b \\ S_{20}^b \\ S_{30}^b \end{bmatrix} \right\} \tag{9}$$

The switching combinations yield 27 states, 19 of which correspond to different voltage vectors in the (α, β) plane [20]. Vectors are divided into three types based on their magnitude: large, medium, and small. Large vectors allow for quick torque and flux fluctuations, while medium vectors provide smoother transient transitions. Small vectors ensure precision flux control and little torque ripple.

Figure 5 illustrates their spatial organization, with big vectors forming the outer hexagon, medium vectors in intermediate places, and small vectors concentrated around the plane's core. Figure 6 shows how the (α, β) plane is divided into twelve equal 30° sectors to allow for real-time stator-flux position and vector selection. This subdivision enhances torque and flux management by reducing vector steps and resulting in more uniform flux trajectories [21], [22].

Figure 4. Structure of the three-level NPC inverter

The primary switching combinations for each phase leg are summarized in Table 1, where “ON” and “OFF” denote conducting and non-conducting states of the power devices, respectively. This topology keeps the DC-link voltage balanced and allows for symmetrical operation. This reduces switching stress and harmonic distortion. The extra voltage level improves current quality and lowers acoustic noise compared to the two-level inverter [23]. When used in DTC, the NPC inverter allows for smoother transitions in torque and flux, a nearly constant switching frequency, and better low-speed stability. This makes it a suitable platform for better control strategies like FDTTC.

2.5. Control rule table for DTC with three-level NPC inverter

In three-level NPC-based DTC, voltage vector selection uses the triplet (C_f, C_T, N) to represent flux error, torque error, and stator-flux sector. This helps choose from 27 switching states (19 unique vectors) [20], [21]. The expanded vector set allows for better control. Large vectors handle quick torque changes, while small and medium vectors reduce switching stress and current distortion. This results in smoother flux paths and a more stable switching frequency [22]-[24]. Table 2 summarizes the sector-based logic. It links each 30° sector to the control action needed for accurate torque regulation and stable drive performance [25], [26].

Figure 5. Space-vector representation of the 27 switching states of the NPC inverter

Figure 6. Sector division of the (α, β) flux plane for three-level NPC inverter switching

Table 1. Switching combinations and corresponding output levels for a single NPC inverter leg

Switching state	S_{i1}	S_{i2}	S_{i3}	S_{i4}	Output voltage V_i
+1	ON	ON	ON	OFF	$E/2$
0	OFF	OFF	ON	ON	0
-1	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	$-E/2$

Table 2. Switching table for DTC with a three-level NPC inverter

		N_1		N_2		N_7		N_8			
C_{Te}/C_r	1	0									
+2	V_5	V_8	+2	V_5	V_8	+2	V_{14}	V_{17}	+2	V_{14}	V_{17}
+1	V_4	V_7	+1	V_4	V_7	+1	V_{13}	V_{16}	+1	V_{13}	V_{16}
0	V_{19}	V_{20}	0	V_{20}	V_{19}	0	V_{19}	V_{20}	0	V_{20}	V_{19}
-1	V_{16}	V_{13}	-1	V_{16}	V_{13}	-1	V_7	V_4	-1	V_7	V_4
-2	V_{17}	V_{14}	-2	V_2	V_{17}	-2	V_8	V_5	-2	V_{11}	V_5
		N_3		N_4		N_9		N_{10}			
C_{Te}/C_r	1	0									
+2	V_8	V_{11}	+2	V_8	V_{11}	+2	V_{17}	V_2	+2	V_{17}	V_2
+1	V_7	V_{10}	+1	V_7	V_{10}	+1	V_{16}	V_1	+1	V_{16}	V_1
0	V_{19}	V_{20}	0	V_{20}	V_{19}	0	V_{19}	V_{20}	0	V_{20}	V_{19}
-1	V_1	V_{16}	-1	V_1	V_{16}	-1	V_{10}	V_7	-1	V_{10}	V_7
-2	V_2	V_{17}	-2	V_5	V_2	-2	V_{11}	V_8	-2	V_{14}	V_{11}
		N_5		N_6		N_{11}		N_{12}			
C_{Te}/C_r	1	0									
+2	V_{11}	V_{14}	+2	V_{11}	V_{14}	+2	V_2	V_5	+2	V_2	V_5
+1	V_{10}	V_{13}	+1	V_{10}	V_{13}	+1	V_1	V_4	+1	V_1	V_4
0	V_{19}	V_{20}	0	V_{20}	V_{19}	0	V_{19}	V_{20}	0	V_{20}	V_{19}
-1	V_4	V_1	-1	V_4	V_1	-1	V_{13}	V_{10}	1	V_{13}	V_{10}
-2	V_5	V_2	-2	V_8	V_5	-2	V_{14}	V_{11}	-2	V_{17}	V_{14}

2.6. IP speed controller synthesis

The IP speed controller is widely used in high-performance IM drives for its fast dynamics and its ability to eliminate zeros in the closed-loop transfer function, ensuring a continuous torque reference during transients [27], [28]. As shown in Figure 7, the speed error $\Omega^*(s) - \Omega(s)$ is processed through proportional and integral paths scaled by $K_{\Omega p}$, $K_{\Omega i}$ respectively, to generate the reference torque $\Gamma_r(s)$ which governs the machine's electromagnetic response [29]. The mechanical dynamics of the IM can be modeled as:

$$F(s) = \frac{1}{Js+f} \quad (10)$$

assuming no external load disturbances $T_r = 0$, the closed-loop transfer function between reference speed $\Omega^*(s)$ and actual speed $\Omega(s)$ is given by [30]:

$$\frac{\Omega(s)}{\Omega^*(s)} = \frac{1}{\frac{\tau_1}{g_1 K_{\Omega i}} s^2 + \frac{1}{g_1 K_{\Omega i}} s + 1} \quad (11)$$

where the parameters τ_1 and g_1 are defined by:

$$\tau_1 = \frac{J}{K_{\Omega p} + f} \quad (12)$$

$$g_1 = \frac{K_{\Omega p}}{K_{\Omega p} + f} \quad (13)$$

here, $K_{\Omega p}$ and $K_{\Omega i}$ denote the proportional and integral gains of the IP controller, respectively. To achieve an aperiodic speed response, the controller gains must satisfy:

$$K_{\Omega i} = \frac{1}{4g_1\tau_1} \quad (14)$$

and under these conditions, the equivalent time constant of the closed-loop dynamics becomes:

$$\tau_2 = 2\tau_1 \quad (15)$$

consequently, the proportional gain is obtained as (16).

$$K_{\Omega p} = \frac{J - \tau_1 f}{\tau_1} \quad (16)$$

This systematic tuning method ensures smooth torque response, strong disturbance rejection, and stable operation across a wide range of speeds. The IP controller thus provides an effective balance between simplicity, robustness, and dynamic accuracy in DTC–NPC-based drives [27], [30].

Figure 7. Closed-loop speed regulation using an IP controller

3. FUZZY DIRECT TORQUE CONTROL

3.1. Principle of FDTC

A combination of hysteresis comparators and fixed switching tables, conventional DTC has poor low-speed efficiency, variable switching frequency, and torque ripple. By substituting an FIS for them, the FDTC approach solves these problems and permits adaptive and continuous voltage-vector selection [31]–[33]. To find the ideal inverter vector that minimizes flux and torque deviations while maintaining neutral-point balance, the fuzzy block in the proposed FDTC–NPC scheme, as illustrated in Figure 8, processes the stator flux error Δ^1 , torque error $\Delta\Gamma$, and stator flux angle $\theta \in [-\pi, \pi]$.

The input variables of the fuzzy system are defined as (17).

$$\Delta\Phi_s = \Phi_s^* - \Phi_s \quad \Delta\Gamma_e = \Gamma_e^* - \Gamma_e \quad (17)$$

Where Φ_s^* and Γ_e^* are the reference stator flux and torque, respectively. The control objective is to minimize both errors within the permissible tolerance band: $\min\{|\Delta\Phi_s|, |\Delta\Gamma_e|\}$. The fuzzy inference mechanism processes these inputs through a rule base that relates flux and torque errors to a corresponding output voltage vector $V_{\alpha\beta}$:

$$V_{\alpha\beta} = f(\Delta\Phi_s, \Delta\Gamma_e, \theta_s) \quad (18)$$

The fuzzy mapping function $f(\cdot)$ directly synthesizes the optimal voltage vector from expert rules and the sector index. This intelligent selection yields smoother electromagnetic transients and inherent adaptability to nonlinearities, culminating in a marked reduction of torque ripple, a quasi-constant switching frequency, and enhanced low-speed stability, all without incurring significant computational overhead [34].

3.2. Fuzzy inference mechanism, rule base design, and NPC voltage vector decision process

The main idea of the proposed FDTC-NPC scheme is a FIS that replaces the traditional hysteresis comparators and switching table. This smart layer continuously maps the stator-flux error $\Delta\Phi_s$, the torque error $\Delta\Gamma_e$, and stator flux sector θ_s into the best NPC voltage vector. This improves torque smoothness, reduces ripple, and keeps a nearly constant switching frequency [35], [36]. The inputs are fuzzified using two levels for flux (Negative, Positive), five for torque (NL, NS, Z, PS, PL), and twelve 30° sectors for the flux angle, as shown in Figure 9. A rule-based approach, created from the drive's dynamic behavior, determines the best voltage vector to reduce errors and keep neutral-point balance. Each fuzzy rule follows the form:

$$R_i = \text{if } (\Delta\Phi_s = A_j) \text{ and } (\Delta\Gamma_e = B_k) \text{ and } (\theta_s = S_l) \text{ then } (V_{\alpha\beta} = V_m) \quad (19)$$

Where A_j , B_k and S_l represent fuzzy sets for flux, torque, and sector, and V_m denotes one of the 27 possible inverter vectors.

$$V_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\int_{\Omega} \mu(V) V dV}{\int_{\Omega} \mu(V) dV} \quad (20)$$

This enables seamless transitions between vectors and prevents oscillations of torque. The entire rule base can be viewed as a whole from Table 3, it maps each of the twelve regions $N_1 - N_{12}$ to individual control actions. The logic for these selections considers high voltage vectors for torque correction as its top choice, followed by medium and finally small voltage vectors for fine-tuned control [37], [38].

Figure 8. Structure of the proposed FDTC scheme for a three-level NPC inverter-fed IM

In the FDTC scheme, output membership functions are assigned directly to the inverter's voltage vectors. This method allows for flexible decision-making and removes the sudden state changes common in hysteresis comparators. The outcome is a smoother torque response, less flux oscillation, and better steady-state performance in three-level NPC inverter-fed drives [16], [21], [25].

Figure 9. Membership functions of the fuzzy controller input and output variables: (a) membership functions of stator-flux error, (b) membership functions of torque error, (c) membership functions for stator-flux angle, and (d) membership functions of the output control variable

Table 3. Rule-based switching table for FDTC (Each 30° sector defines the voltage-vector selection based on flux and torque fuzzy states)

N_1		N_2		N_7		N_8	
C_{Te}/C_r	1 0						
PI	$V_5 V_8$	PI	$V_5 V_8$	PI	$V_{14} V_{17}$	PI	$V_{14} V_{17}$
PS	$V_4 V_7$	PS	$V_4 V_7$	PS	$V_{13} V_{16}$	PS	$V_{13} V_{16}$
Z	$V_{19} V_{20}$	Z	$V_{20} V_{19}$	Z	$V_{19} V_{20}$	Z	$V_{20} V_{19}$
NS	$V_{16} V_{13}$	NS	$V_{16} V_{13}$	NS	$V_7 V_4$	NS	$V_7 V_4$
NL	$V_{17} V_{14}$	NL	$V_2 V_{17}$	NL	$V_8 V_5$	NL	$V_{11} V_5$
N_3		N_4		N_9		N_{10}	
C_{Te}/C_r	1 0						
PI	$V_8 V_{11}$	PI	$V_8 V_{11}$	PI	$V_{17} V_2$	PI	$V_{17} V_2$
PS	$V_7 V_{10}$	PS	$V_7 V_{10}$	PS	$V_{16} V_1$	PS	$V_{16} V_1$
Z	$V_{19} V_{20}$	Z	$V_{20} V_{19}$	Z	$V_{19} V_{20}$	Z	$V_{20} V_{19}$
NS	$V_1 V_{16}$	NS	$V_1 V_{16}$	NS	$V_{10} V_7$	NS	$V_{10} V_7$
NL	$V_2 V_{17}$	NL	$V_5 V_2$	NL	$V_{11} V_8$	NL	$V_{14} V_{11}$
N_5		N_6		N_{11}		N_{12}	
C_{Te}/C_r	1 0						
PI	$V_{11} V_{14}$	PI	$V_{11} V_{14}$	PI	$V_2 V_5$	PI	$V_2 V_5$
PS	$V_{10} V_{13}$	PS	$V_{10} V_{13}$	PS	$V_1 V_4$	PS	$V_1 V_4$
Z	$V_{19} V_{20}$	Z	$V_{20} V_{19}$	Z	$V_{19} V_{20}$	Z	$V_{20} V_{19}$
NS	$V_4 V_1$	NS	$V_4 V_1$	NS	$V_{13} V_{10}$	NS	$V_{13} V_{10}$
NL	$V_5 V_2$	NL	$V_8 V_5$	NL	$V_{14} V_{11}$	NL	$V_{17} V_{14}$

3.3. PI-fuzzy speed controller synthesis

The FDTC-NPC machine’s performance is controlled by its external speed loop. In order to improve the flexibility and overcome the fixed-gain constraint of a traditional IP controller, the paper also introduces a control strategy using a hybrid control approach called the “PI-fuzzy regulator”. It combines the proportional-integral control strategy for accurate control in a short span of time with the ‘fuzzy’ action of the fuzzy inference system [39], [40]. Figure 10 shows the process of controlling the speeds using the error in speeds, i.e., the actual speed, $e = \Omega^* - \Omega^*$, the actual speed’s derivative de/dt , of the speeds. The result’s influence on the proportional integral gains is utilized, which acts on the actual speed reference, ensuring an optimal torque [41].

The fuzzification process defines seven linguistic terms for each input variable (NB, NM, NS, Z, PS, PM, PB). Fuzzification uses triangular membership functions with seven linguistic terms for all variables: NB: negative big, NM: negative medium, NS: negative small, PB: positive big, PS: positive small, PM: positive medium, and ZR: zero.

Table 4 lists the fuzzy rules that relate the error and its rate of change to control actions, while Figure 11 shows the corresponding membership functions. This rule-based fuzzy structure provides smooth control dynamics with inherent nonlinearity adaptation. By dynamically modulating the control effort, it minimizes overshoot, improves settling time, and enhances disturbance rejection. The resulting PI-fuzzy controller thereby ensures robust adaptive speed regulation across the entire operating range, forming a synergistic integration with the FDTC–NPC scheme [42].

Figure 10. Block diagram of the PI-fuzzy speed controller

Table 4. Fuzzy rules for the PI-fuzzy speed controller
(Each rule defines the output control action according to the error and its derivative)

d_e/e	PB	PM	PS	ZR	NS	NM	NB
NB	EZ	NS	NM	NB	NB	NB	NB
NM	PS	EZ	NS	NM	NB	NB	NB
NS	PM	PS	EZ	NS	NM	NB	NB
ZR	PB	PM	PS	EZ	NS	NM	NB
PS	PB	PB	PM	PS	EZ	NS	NM
PM	PB	PB	PB	PM	PS	EZ	NS
PB	PB	PB	PB	PB	PM	PS	EZ

Figure 11. Membership functions of the PI fuzzy controller inputs and output

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Simulation setup and modeling

The proposed FDTC–NPC system was implemented in MATLAB/Simulink R2022b by integrating the flux and torque estimation blocks, the fuzzy voltage-vector selection mechanism, and the hybrid PI–fuzzy speed regulator introduced in section 3. The total simulation layout is depicted in Figure 12, and Figure 13 illustrates the detailed structure of the fuzzy DTC controller and its coupling with the three-level NPC inverter. The proposed layout provides a practical simulation environment for evaluating the performance of the drive system.

The parameters involved in the simulation process of the electrical, mechanical, and inverter systems are provided in Table 5. The design of the experiment has been conducted in a way that it is able to evaluate the transient response as well as the steady-state response of the induction motor drive system under various loading and speeds. The design of the experiment allows one to make a comparison between the traditional DTC method and the proposed FDTC/NPC method.

Figure 12. MATLAB/Simulink model of the proposed FDTC–NPC induction motor drive

Figure 13. Internal structure of the proposed FDTC scheme

4.2. Test conditions and speed response

Simulations were carried out on a 1.5 kW induction motor over 4 s, with reference speed steps applied at $t = 0.2$ s (600 rpm), $t = 1.4$ s (1000 rpm), and $t = 3$ s (200 rpm). Both the IP and PI-fuzzy controllers were tested under identical conditions for fair comparison. Figure 14 illustrates that although both control methods are tracking well, the PI Fuzzy controller has far better dynamics, since it has quicker convergence, zero overshoot, and smoother transitions. The zoomed graph emphasizes its improved damping and stability when subjected to loading during acceleration and deceleration.

Table 5. IM and inverter parameters used in the simulation

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Rated power	P	1.5	kW
Voltage	V	220/380	V
Number of pair poles	n_p	2	-
Stator resistance	R_s	5.63	Ω
Rotor resistance	R_r	2.62	Ω
Stator self-inductance	L_s	0.018	H
Rotor self-inductance	L_r	0.018	H
Mutual inductance	M	0.20	H
Rotor inertia	J	0.02	kgm ²
Viscous friction coefficient	f	0.0057	N.m.s

Figure 14. Rotor speed response comparison between IP controller and PI-fuzzy controller

4.3. Stator flux response

It follows that Figure 15 compares the stator flux trajectories, which show an almost perfectly circular trajectory with constant amplitude for the proposed FDTC–NPC and the distorted trajectory of conventional DTC. This improvement is due to the NPC's finer voltage resolution and fuzzy decision layer, both of which contribute to easier transitions of flux and less ripple [43].

Figure 15. Stator flux response: (a) conventional DTC and (b) proposed FDTC-NPC strategy

4.4. Stator current response

Figure 16 illustrates the stator current waveforms using conventional DTC and the FDTC-NPC approach. This results in smoother and sinusoidal current waveforms, unlike those produced using conventional DTC, which contain higher distortion and oscillations. This indicates that conventional DTC has poorer current control. This improvement is attributed to the three-level inverter's smaller voltage steps and fuzzy-based vector selection, which reduce current harmonics and switching stress.

Figure 16. Stator current response i_{sa} : (a) conventional DTC and (b) proposed FDTC-NPC strategy

4.5. Electromagnetic torque response

Figure 17 shows a comparison between the electromagnetic torque responses of the conventional DTC and the proposed FDTC-NPC control. The classical DTC presents strong torque ripples and irregular oscillations, while the FDTC-NPC achieves smoother and more stable responses with faster dynamic recovery. Torque ripple is lowered by nearly 25–30% due to fuzzy voltage-vector selection and the extended switching states of the three-level NPC inverter [44]. For clear comparison, the quantitative analysis confirms that torque smoothness is significantly improved by the proposed FDTC-NPC strategy, while current THD is reduced and the settling time is shortened compared with classical DTC [45], [46].

Figure 17. Comparison of electromagnetic torque response and torque ripple: (a) conventional DTC strategy and (b) proposed FDTC-NPC strategy

5. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced the FDTC strategy in IM drives based on a three-level NPC inverter. The strategy replaces the hysteresis comparators and the switching tables of the traditional DTC strategy with a fuzzy inference system. It also incorporates a speed regulator based on a PI-Fuzzy controller. Simulation outcomes have confirmed that the FDTC strategy based on the NPC inverter provides a smoother torque, an improved flux, a reduced torque ripple of around 25–30%, a lower current distortion, and improved speed tracking performance compared to the traditional DTC strategy.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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Jamila Chennane	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that are required to verify the results obtained in this article are available from the corresponding author on a reasonable request. The simulation models and numerical data obtained are made in "MATLAB/Simulink." These models can also be shared for research use.

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